

TECHNOLOGY OF TEACHING METHODS OF WORKING WITH A DICTIONARY TO STUDENTS OF NON- PHILOLOGICAL UNIVERSITIES (IN THE PROCESS OF STUDYING FOREIGN LANGUAGES)

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The article discusses technologies for teaching students of non-philological specialties the effective use of dictionaries when studying foreign languages. The importance of developing skills in working with a dictionary to improve the level of language competence and professional training is emphasized. Methodological recommendations aimed at developing the skills of searching, interpreting and applying lexical information are presented.

The article is devoted to the study of methods of working with a dictionary as an important tool in the study of foreign languages by students of non-philological specialties. Modern approaches to teaching, the integration of digital technologies and their impact on the development of language competencies are considered. The advantages of using dictionaries of various types (paper and electronic) are discussed, as well as the technologies for their use in the educational process.

Modern teaching of foreign languages requires an emphasis on the practical orientation of knowledge. For students of non-philological specialties who do not have a deep linguistic foundation, a dictionary becomes an important tool. However, not all students know how to effectively use this resource, which reduces their success in mastering the language.[1].

The purpose of this article is to present technologies and methodological approaches that contribute to the formation of skills for competent work with a dictionary in the context of educational and professional tasks.

Effective acquisition of a foreign language by students of non-philological specialties requires the development of autonomous skills in working with educational materials, including dictionaries. However, students often do not have sufficient skills to fully use dictionaries, which slows down the process of language learning.

Methods of working with a dictionary have received attention in the works of educators and linguists. Research emphasizes the importance of teaching students the skills of analyzing vocabulary, searching for contextual meanings, and working with phraseological expressions (Nation, 2001). In modern conditions, research on the impact of digital technologies, such as electronic dictionaries and mobile applications, is relevant (Prensky, 2009; Dudeney & Hockly, 2016).

Basic approaches to teaching how to work with a dictionary

Traditional approaches

1. Working with a paper dictionary:

- Analysis of the dictionary structure (words, articles, transcription, examples).
- Completing word search exercises.

2. Contextual search:

- Developing skills in interpreting the meaning of a word depending on the context.

Integration of digital technologies

1. Electronic dictionaries and applications:
 - Use of mobile platforms (Lingvo, WordReference).
 - Development of skills for quick information search.
2. Interactive tasks:
 - Crosswords, simulators and quizzes for strengthening vocabulary.
3. Artificial intelligence technologies:
 - Use of chatbots for word usage practice.
 - Translation and explanatory dictionaries with the function of explaining grammatical features. [2].

Research Methodology:

1. Analysis of students' needs:
 - Questionnaire to identify preferences and level of proficiency in vocabulary skills.
2. Development of learning tasks:
 - Constructing exercises using paper and electronic dictionaries.
3. Practical implementation:
 - Conducting an experiment in a group of students majoring in non-philology.
4. Evaluation of effectiveness:
 - Comparison of students' academic performance before and after using technologies for working with a dictionary.

Working with a dictionary of students of non-philological universities when studying a foreign language requires taking into account the specifics of their future professional activity, interests and level of language training. Methods of working with a dictionary are aimed at developing lexical skills, understanding the meanings of words and their use in the appropriate context.

Let's consider the main approaches:

1. Contextual word learning

- Reading and analyzing texts on the subject: Providing students with texts related to their professional field helps them master terminology. Students find unfamiliar words, analyze their meaning in context, and create topic-specific dictionaries.
- Working with collocations: Exercises on studying stable combinations of words (e.g., "make a decision", "carry out an experiment") contribute to better memorization and correct use.

2. Developing topic-specific dictionaries

- Lexical maps: Creating schemes or clusters of words by topic. For example, for engineers, words related to mechanical engineering or IT.
- Discipline-specific glossary: Creating a glossary with professional terms and their translations.
- Electronic dictionaries: Using online platforms to create interactive dictionaries where students can add definitions, examples, and audio files with pronunciations.

3. Vocabulary Activation

- Sentence Creation: Students create sentences or mini-stories with new words.
- Role Play: Using words from thematic dictionaries in professional dialogues, discussions or simulations of work situations.

- Translation: Translating professional texts into the native language and back to consolidate vocabulary.

4. Game Methods

- Crosswords and Quizzes: Create crosswords based on professional vocabulary.
- Flashcards: Use flashcards to memorize words. Electronic versions (such as Anki) allow you to add images and audio.
- Vocab Games: Games such as "guess the word" or "association" to reinforce words in a playful way.

5. Etymological approach

- Word analysis by composition: Analysis of roots, prefixes and suffixes, which helps to understand the origin and meaning of words.
- Comparison with native language: Identification of analogies between foreign and native words to facilitate memorization.

6. Integration with ICT

- Use of online dictionaries and translators: For example, WordReference, Linguee, Reverso, which provide examples of usage in context.
- Vocabulary learning apps: Duolingo, Quizlet and Memrise to consolidate words via mobile devices.
- Educational videos and podcasts: Watching professional lectures and podcasts to perceive terminology by ear.

7. Independent work of students

- Maintaining a personal dictionary: Each student writes down new words, example sentences and associations.
- Reflection: Regular repetition of written words with analysis of how often they are used in speech.

8. Control and motivation

- Testing: Checking the assimilation of words through tests or control tasks.
- Goal Setting: Setting short-term goals to learn a certain number of words.

The dictionary performs a number of functions:

- Informational function — providing the meaning of a word, its grammatical and phonetic characteristics.
- Educational function — developing language intuition, expanding vocabulary.
- Instrumental function — using the dictionary as a tool for translating, editing texts and preparing professional documentation.

For students of non-philological universities, the dictionary becomes an indispensable assistant when completing assignments related to professional topics.

Problems with using dictionaries by students.

Many students face difficulties:

- Ignorance of the dictionary structure (searching for words, understanding transcription, grammatical notations, etc.).
- Inability to choose the appropriate type of dictionary (printed, electronic, thematic).
- Slow work speed, especially under time constraints.
- Errors in interpreting polysemantic words or set expressions. [3].

To develop skills in working with a dictionary, teachers can use the following approaches:

1. Teaching the structure of a dictionary

- ✓ Conducting practical classes on analyzing the structure of various types of dictionaries.
 - ✓ Familiarizing students with the symbols used in dictionaries (transcription, grammatical abbreviations, style notes).
2. Developing skills for quickly searching for information
 - ✓ Exercises for finding words in a limited time.
 - ✓ Working with alphabetical and thematic principles of ordering.
 3. Developing the ability to interpret information
 - ✓ Analysis of the meanings of polysemantic words in context.
 - ✓ Exercises for distinguishing synonyms, antonyms, and paronyms.
 4. Using electronic resources
 - ✓ Familiarization with modern online dictionaries and translators (Linguee, Reverso, WordReference, etc.).
 - ✓ Ability to use applications and software, including voice input and searching for examples. [4].

Practical exercises:

- Contextual analysis: students receive phrases where one word is used in different meanings and must find the appropriate meaning in the dictionary.
- Find it faster: students compete to find the meaning of a word or its grammatical form faster.
- Creating a glossary: students create topical glossaries using several sources.

Teaching students of non-philological specialties methods of working with a dictionary is an important aspect of developing language competence. The integration of modern technologies with traditional approaches allows for a significant increase in the effectiveness of the educational process. [5].

Formation of skills of working with a dictionary is an important part of teaching foreign languages to students of non-philological specialties. It not only develops their language competence, but also increases professional readiness. The use of modern technologies and methods contributes to an increase in interest in learning a language and improvement of learning results.

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